

Uncovering the bacterial protein toolbox targeting the human glycome

Angelina S. Palma^{1,2}

1. UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

2. Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

angelina.palma@fct.unl.pt

Glycans are essential players in bacterial-host interactions comprising recognition sites for both commensal and pathogenic bacteria, contributing to shaping the resident bacterial population at the gut epithelial mucosal surface. Emerging research is uncovering gut bacterial mechanisms that use host glycans as nutrients or degrade them during pathogen invasion. A paradigm in human microbiome research relates to the ability of some commensal bacteria, such as *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* and *B. caccae*, to forage on mucin O-glycans from the mucus protecting layer of the gut epithelia, using these as nutrients or attachment sites, enhancing their competitiveness to colonise, particularly in a low fibre diet. Commensal bacteria that can recognize host-glycans influence not only the host response but also colonic health, promoting states of dysbiosis and susceptibility to infection.

How mucin O-glycans are differentially exploited by human microbiome bacteria and influence the crosstalk with the host largely remains to be elucidated at the molecular level. In this communication, I will overview the characterization of newly identified glycan-binding proteins from these bacteria, which are encoded by sets of co-regulated genes termed *polysaccharide utilization loci* systems (PULs) targeting a specific glycan structure. Through sequence and structural bioinformatic analysis of the bacterial genomes, we selected putative glycan-binding proteins for high-throughput production and ligand discovery using glycan microarrays. Structural characterization of proteins targeting mucin O-GalNAc-Thr/Ser cores and Tn antigen by X-ray crystallography led to uncovering their molecular determinants for mucin O-glycan recognition. These and their associated putative O-glycan selective catalytic domains are being investigated for their biotechnological exploitation as a molecular protein toolbox to target human glycans. We anticipate this study to help understand the role of commensal bacteria in gut health and in designing new therapeutic and diagnostic strategies.

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